

DOES JOB ENGAGEMENT PLAY A MEDIATING ROLE IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN JOB CRAFTING AND JOB PERFORMANCE?

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Abstract

Human resources have a central role in the development of the organization/company. The essence of HR in an organization is a form of all the potential that exists in humans which shows the qualities possessed that can be utilized to gain a sustainable competitive advantage and win the competition. The research objective was to examine the direct and indirect effects of Job crafting behavior on Job Performance through Job Engagement. The research sample is 320 employees from 40 creative industries/economy in Indonesia. The sampling technique used is multi-stage sampling, the data analysis technique used is the Structural Equation Model, PLS. The results of the study show that Job crafting behavior has a direct and indirect effect on Job Performance through Job engagement. Job engagement acts as partial mediating in this regard. Theoretical and practical implications are presented of this paper.

Keywords: Job Crafting, Job Engagement, Job Performance, Creative Economy

INTRUDUCTION

Human resources have a central role in the development of the organization/company. The essence of HR in an organization is a form of all the potential that exists in humans which shows the qualities possessed that can be utilized to gain a sustainable competitive advantage and win the competition which is very necessary in an era of very tight competition both in the local and global markets.

Furthermore, human capital theory (Becker, 2002), in the form of knowledge, information, ideas, skills, and health, etc.) is by far the most important form of resource in the modern economy (Sunyoto, 2012); closely related and able to increase added value and have an impact on achieving organizational goals efficiently (Mathis & Jackson, 2011), but objective conditions show the opposite result that the performance of employees in Indonesia is relatively

low. (education.kompas.com, 2019); including in the ASEAN region (source: International Labor Organization (ILO) data, 2022).

To contribute and provide solutions to this crucial problem, it is necessary to have participation and concern from all components of the nation, including universities. Lecturers and students as the spearhead of the campus should be involved in this problem, by carrying out the tri dharma of higher education. It is within this framework that this research was conducted with a focus on improving employee performance in the creative industry sector in Indonesia, by examining the antecedent factors that influence employee performance. The creative industry has made a significant contribution to state revenue, especially in the post-covid 19 era. The creative industry has begun to rise to catch up to the downturn in the co-19 era.

The results of empirical studies recommend that improving employee performance is influenced by 3 main factors: individual factors, psychological factors, and organizational factors (Mangkunegara, 2010). Individual factors are represented by Job Crafting, psychological factors are represented by job Engagement, and job performance is represented by organizational factors.

Job crafting provides space for employees to design, create and provide job interpretations by modifying job characteristics and work environment to better suit individual characteristics, passion, capacities and abilities and qualities; job crafting has a significant positive impact on employee performance (Petrou, et al., 2012); Guan & Frenkel (2018)); provide space, opportunities and opportunities that enable employees to more proactively adjust and structure their work, become more participative, creative and innovative, prefer challenges and take full responsibility for work (Petrou et al., 2018), but Lichtenthaler et al. (2018), proved conflicting research results.

We use job-based resource theory to formulate hypotheses the research problem formulation. This theory explains that the results of employees' efforts, creativity and innovation are in the form of knowledge, abilities, competencies, human resource quality, etc. is an intangible resource that is unique, superior, rare and valuable which must be continuously developed and developed to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage and win the competition in a sustainable manner (Kailiang Dai, and Xinyu Qin (2016). This theory is supported by: Liang, G.Q. et al. (2015); Chen, A.Q. (2012); Wan, Z. et al. (2011); Gao, J.L. et al. (2015).

Another very important thing to discuss related to employee performance is job engagement. According to the 2020 Strategic Human Resource Management Report, more than 85% of employees are not involved in their workplace, even though it clearly shows the link between employee engagement and performance. There is no specific strategy that can improve employee performance quickly and instantly. The essence of this issue is how the business is managed effectively and efficiently, how to improve skills, and motivate employees; how to make each individual employee willing and able to work accordingly with the vision and mission of the company. The following empirical studies (see: Schaufeli, et al. (2012); Lu, C. et al. (2014); Rich, B. L. et al. (2010); Setyawati, S. M. (2019); Petrou, P. et al. (2019); J., A. (2014). , prove the link between the two.

The novelty of this research lies in the implemented research theme/title in the creative economy/industry in an integrated manner includes 3 main factors: individual factors, psychological factors, and organizational factors are still scarce (1); There is a gap literature, namely different and even contradictory research results regarding the existence of these three variables - some place these variables as independent, intervening and even dependent variables (2) Employee Performance Model (Job performance) which is built by several main factors that are complete and integrated, carried out in the creative industry sector in the sector is still rare (3).

The purpose of this paper is to produce a Job Performance model that is built from 2 concepts, namely Job crafting behavior and job engagement which is implemented in the creative economy in East Java, Indonesia.

With this research it is hoped that it will be able to clarify the results of previous studies that are different and even contradictory, this research also aims to expand this literature by adding job engagement as mediating role in the relationship between the two concepts. It is hoped that this paper will be able to contribute to policy makers in the creative economy sector in Indonesia that to improve optimal employee performance requires maximum effort to increase job crafting and job engagement.

Creative Economy is an economic concept that prioritizes individual creativity and information in the form of knowledge, creative thinking, and human resource ideas to create something new that has added commercial value to develop a sustainable economic system; characterized by: individual creativity, distributed directly/indirectly, easily changed, no limit, following trends, based on cultural values. Industry/creative economy in Indonesia includes: food/beverage, Fashion, Crafts, Fine Arts, Interior Design, Film, Visual Communication Design, Television and Radio, Publishing, Architecture, Application and Game Developer, Advertising, Music Photography, Performing Arts, Product Design.

The importance of raising the creative economy/industry as an object of research is: (1) the creative economy plays a critical, crucial and significant role in the growth, development and development of the Indonesian nation's economy, (2) The increase in the creative economy has an impact on community resilience. National economy. (3) The era of the industrial revolution 4.0 made the creative economy a strategy to win global competition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Job Crafting Behaviors

Wrzesniewski and Dutton, are the initiators of the concept of job crafting which is interpreted as physical and psychological changes made by employees in order to create new work relationships by changing the work limits set by the company/organization (Wrzesniewski & Dutton (2003); is a personal initiative to design Re-work by creating work requirements, relationships, and a conducive work environment to achieve optimal performance, work behavior that contributes positively to the organization/company, role innovation and role development (Bakker and W. B. Schaufeli (2013); Dvorak (2014); is a form of employee

proactive behavior in the form of initiative, creativity, and personal innovation to design and make changes related to work physically and mentally covering 3 dimensions, namely: task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting; and includes techniques in doing work to make it more meaningful.

2. The concept of Job Engagement

Job Engagement is the proactive and positive attitudes of employees regarding behavior at work; employees can express themselves totally both physically, cognitively, affectively, and emotionally, so they are able to find the nature and meaning of work well; proud to be part of the company, working optimally and even extra to achieve company goals effectively and efficiently; is a form of employee proactive behavior in the form of self-initiative, anticipatory actions that aim to give meaning to work by redesigning work (in Parker & Collins, 2010). Employees with high involvement work more enthusiastically, energetically, enthusiastically, creatively, innovatively, productively, and have a strong will to perform optimally, are satisfied and committed (Bakker & Leiter, 2010; Bakker & Demerouti, 2008).

3. The concept of Job Performance

Job performance is the result of work achieved by employees in quantity and quality within a certain period of time by completing assigned tasks/obligations, which is done by comparing actual performance with performance standards (Wiratama & Sintaasih, 2013; Sopiah, 2018). When a company/organization as an employer fails to fulfill promises to employees by meeting the needs of employees, decreased performance, and low commitment and even further, employee intentions to leave the organization can arise (Robbins & Judge, 2015). Employee attachment to work and organization makes employees more productive and efficient. High employee performance reflects the psychological relationship of employees to their organization to devote all their abilities to the progress of the organization (Adiftiya, 2014).

4. Job Crafting Behaviors, Job Engagement, and Job Performance

Empirical studies prove that the relationship between the three variables is significantly positive, both directly and indirectly (Van Wingerden, et al. (2017); Thun, S. et al. (2018). According to Schaufeli and Bakker (in Bakker & Leiter, 2010); job crafting influence on job engagement. Employees who reflect job crafting are indicated to quickly adapt to changes in the workplace, and are considered to help success in strategies for organizational development (Lee & Lee, 2018). Vogt, K. et al., (2016); Weseler, D. et al. (2016), proved job crafting is related to work engagement and employee performance. Rudolph, C. W. et al., (2017); Miraglia, M. et al. (2017); Geldenhuys, M. et al. (2020) proved that job crafting has an effect on employee performance. Oprea, B.T., Barzin, L., Virga, D., Iliescu, D., & Rusu, A. (2019); Petrou, P., Demerouti, E., Peeters, M. C., Schaufeli, W. B., & Hetland, J. (2012), shows that job crafting is related with employee engagement. Lu, C. qin, Wang, H. jiang, Lu, J. jing, Du, D. yang, & Bakker, A. B. (2014); Setyawati, S. M. (2019), proves that job crafting is related to performance. Van Wingerden, J., Derks, D., & Bakker, A. B. (2015); Truxillo, D. M., Cadiz, D. M., Rineer, J. R., Zaniboni, S., & Fraccaroli, F. (2012); Tims, M., Bakker, A. B., Derks, D.,

& van Rhenen, W. (2013); Rich, B. L., Lepine, J. A., & Crawford, E. R. (2010), proved that job engagement has an impact on employee performance.

Based on theoretical and empirical studies that have been carried out, the hypothesis developed:

- H.1. Job Crafting Behaviors affect Job Engagement
- H.2. Job Crafting Behaviors affect Job Performance
- H.3. Job Engagement has an effect on Job Performance
- H.4. Job Crafting Behaviors affect Job Performance through Job Engagement

METHOD

Design Research

This research uses a quantitative approach and is a type of explanation research. There are 4 variables in this study, namely: there is 1 exogenous variable, namely job crafting (X); 1 intervening variable, namely Job engagement (Z); and 1 endogenous variable, namely Job Performance (Y). The research framework is described as follows:

Performance (Y). Adapun research framework digambarkan sebagai berikut:

Figure 1: Research Framework

Until and Procedure

The research was conducted on employees working in 40 creative industries/economy (handicrafts and batik craftsmen) in East Java, Indonesia. The number of samples is 320 people (155 women, 165 men), obtained by proportional random sampling. Data collection was carried out using a closed instrument, lasting for 4 months which was carried out in 2 ways offline as much as 55% and 45% was carried out online by filling in the link provided which lasted for 4 months from December to March 2023. The instrument used was a closed questionnaire with 5 alternative answers (1) strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

Measurement

(1) Job Crafting Job crafting is measured by a scale from Tims, et al. (2012); Slemp et al. (2013); Leana, et al. (2009), with a three-dimensional model, namely: task crafting, cognitive crafting, and relational crafting, is broken down into 9 statement items.

(2) Job Engagement, measured by the Utrecht Work Engagement Scale; Schaufeli, et al. (2006), with three dimensions: vigor (3 items), dedication (3 items), and absorption (3 items), a total of 9 statement items.

(3) Job performance, adopting and modifying Bernadin, HJ & Russel, JEA (1993), includes 6 dimensions: quality (2 items), quantity (2 items), timeliness (2 items), cost effectiveness (2 items), need for supervision (2 items), Interpersonal impact.(2 items), a total of 12 statement items.

Data Analysis

Data analysis was carried out using partial least square analysis, SmartPLS, by conducting 2 tests, namely (a) test: (a) Measurement Model Evaluation (outer loading) and b) inner loading test (Ghozali & Latan, 2014). In evaluating outer loading, 3 (three) tests were used, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability. In evaluating the inner model, 3 (three) tests are used, namely R-Square, F-Square, and Bootstrapping.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Result

Before presenting the results of the descriptive statistical test, the characteristics of the respondents are first explained as follows: The study was conducted on employees from 60 creative economies/industries (handycrafts and batik craftsmen) spread across East Java, Indonesia. The number of samples is 320 people with composition: 165 (52%) women, and 155 (48%) men); Education Level: < SMA/equivalent (45%), Diploma/equivalent (32%), S1 (19%), S2 (5%); Work experience: < 5 years (11%), 6-10 years (19%), 11-20 years (21%), 21-30 years (26%), >31 years (23%).

1. Descriptive Statistical Test Results

Table 1: Conditions X, Z and Y

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
X	320	29.00	45.00	37.6156	.18463	3.30276
Z	320	29.00	45.00	37.7844	.22321	3.99299
Y	320	28.00	50.00	41.3375	.24640	4.40773
Valid N (listwise)	320					

Source: Data Processed by Researchers Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Table 1. above explains that:

- 1) The Job Crafting variable is in good/high condition with a minimum statistical value of 29.0, a maximum statistical value of 45.0; mean = 37.6156. It means that Job Crafting is perceived by high employees. Creative industry employees in Indonesia have good/high task crafting, Cognitive Crafting and Relational Crafting.

2) Work Engagement, categorized as high with a minimum statistic score of 29.0, a maximum statistic score of 45.0; mean = 37.7844. This means that creative industry employees in Indonesia have high job engagement. Employees fulfill high vigor, Dedication and Absorption.

3) Job performance, categorized as high/good, with a minimum statistic score of 28.0, a maximum statistic score of 50.0; mean = 41.3375. This means that the leadership assesses that employees at work have paid attention to quantity/work targets, quality, set time, efficiency and the ability to establish good relationships with other parties.

2. Smart PLS SEM test results

Smart PLS SEM test, performs 2 main activities, namely: performs outer loading and inner loading tests, as follows:

a) Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer loading)

In evaluating the outer model, 3 (three) tests were used, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity, and composite reliability.

1. Convergent validity

The convergent validity value is seen from the outer loading value, as follows:

Tabel 1: Outer Loading

	Job Crafting	Job Engagement	Job Performance
JC1	0.851		
JC2	0.903		
JC3	0.838		
JC4	0.844		
JC5	0.905		
JC6	0.844		
JC7	0.764		
JC8	0.773		
JC9	0.731		
JE1		0.887	
JE2		0.869	
JE3		0.751	
JE4		0.879	
JE5		0.708	
JE6		0.871	
JE7		0.858	
JE8		0.722	
JE9		0.882	
JP1			0.868
JP2			0.839
JP3			0.716
JP4			0.846
JP5			0.846
JP6			0.841
JP7			0.849

JP8			0.849
JP9			0.718
JP10			0.808
JP11			0.861
JP12			0.844
POS1			
POS2			
POS3			
POS4			
POS5			
POS6			
POS7			
POS8			
POS9			
POS10			

Source: Data Processed by Researchers Using SmartPLS, (2023)

Based on the results of the convergent validity test, the outer loading value of all variables shows a value of > 0.60 which can be interpreted that all variables are declared valid (Hair et al, 2019). Furthermore, there is another way of testing convergent validity, namely by looking at the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). The AVE value must be greater than 0.5 (Ghozali & Latan, 2014). The following is the AVE value described in the following table:

Table 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variabel	AVE	Keterangan
Job Crafting (X)	0.689	Valid
Job Performance (Y)	0,681	Valid
Job Engagement (Z)	0,686	Valid

Source: Data Processed by Researchers Using SmartPLS, (2023)

Table 2 above explains that the AVE acquisition value for each variable meets the criteria, namely > 0.5 and is declared valid. So it can be concluded that there are no problems in testing convergent validity. The outer loading evaluation test can be seen in discriminant validity, namely the cross loading value. The following is the cross loading value described in the following table:

2. Discriminatory validity

The discriminate validity value is seen from the Cross Loading value, the following are the results:

Table 3: Cross Loading

	Job Crafting	Job Engagement	Job performance
JC1	0.851	0.854	0.865
JC2	0.903	0.783	0.732
JC3	0.838	0.711	0.627
JC4	0.844	0.846	0.854
JC5	0.905	0.786	0.736
JC6	0.844	0.719	0.635
JC7	0.764	0.705	0.712
JC8	0.773	0.879	0.838
JC9	0.731	0.743	0.849
JE1	0.775	0.887	0.844
JE2	0.770	0.869	0.806
JE3	0.737	0.751	0.853
JE4	0.766	0.879	0.827
JE5	0.763	0.708	0.717
JE6	0.775	0.871	0.814
JE7	0.855	0.858	0.862
JE8	0.845	0.722	0.635
JE9	0.771	0.882	0.828
JP1	0.851	0.855	0.868
JP2	0.722	0.734	0.839
JP3	0.763	0.706	0.716
JP4	0.729	0.742	0.846
JP5	0.748	0.861	0.846
JP6	0.770	0.880	0.841
JP7	0.715	0.733	0.849
JP8	0.731	0.745	0.849
JP9	0.762	0.703	0.718
JP10	0.763	0.859	0.808
JP11	0.846	0.849	0.861
JP12	0.744	0.860	0.844
POS1	0.897	0.779	0.728
POS2	0.766	0.709	0.718
POS3	0.770	0.883	0.842
POS4	0.733	0.750	0.849
POS5	0.770	0.878	0.837
POS6	0.764	0.707	0.711
POS7	0.846	0.720	0.641
POS8	0.895	0.777	0.724
POS9	0.767	0.712	0.722
POS10	0.840	0.712	0.627

Source: Data Processed by Researchers Using SmartPLS, (2023)

Based on Table 3, the results of the discriminant validity test, seen from the cross loading value of the indicators of the latent variables, have a greater cross loading value than the other variables. Therefore, it can be concluded that latent variables have good discriminant validity.

In order to test and measure reliability, two methods can be used, namely using composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha which is shown in the following table:

3. Composite Reliability Value

In order to test and measure reliability, two methods can be used, namely using composite reliability and Cronbach's alpha which is shown in the following table:

Table 4: Composite Reliability Value

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Job Crafting (X)	0.948	0.952	Valid
Job Performance (Y)	0.957	0.962	Valid
Job Engagement (Z)	0.942	0.951	Valid

Table 4 above explains that: (1) the composite reliability value of 3 variables > 0.7 , meaning that all variables meet the rules as good composite reliability. (2) The value of Cronbach's alpha 3 variables > 0.7 , meaning that the three variables meet the requirements for Cronbach's alpha. So, it can be concluded that all constructs have high reliability.

b) Evaluation of the Structural Model (Inner Model)

In the evaluation of the inner model, 3 (three) tests are used, namely R-Square, F-Square, and Bootstrapping. The results of the calculation of R-Square are presented in the following table:

1. R-Square test

Table 5: R-Square

Variabel	R-Square
Job Engagement (Z)	0.900
Job Performance (Y)	0.937

The test in table 5 above shows that the R-Square value for the Job Performance variable is 0.937 or the equivalent of 93.7%. The results show that the Job Crafting variables influence by contributing to form the Job Performance variable by 90%, while the remaining 10% is influenced by other variables not explained in this study. The R-Square value is included in the high influential category. The Job Engagement variable has an R-Square value of 0.900 or the equivalent of 90% which indicates that the Job Engagement variable has a contribution to the effect of Job Crafting on Job Performance by 90%. The R-Square value is included in the high influential category. Next, the F-Square value is presented:

2. F-Square value

Table 6: F-Square

Variabel	X	Z	Y
Job Crafting (X)			
Job Engagement (Z)		0.386	
Job Performance (Y)			0.590

Table 6 shows the results of the F-Square Job Crafting (X) test for Job Engagement (Z) has a value of 0.386 which is high. Furthermore, the results of the F-Square Job Engagement (Z) test on Job Performance (Y) have a value of 0.590 which is classified as having a high influence

3. Bootstrapping

Figure 2: Image of Bootstrapping Results

(Source: Data Processed by Researchers Using SmartPLS, 2023)

Table 7: Table of Bootstrapping Test Results

Variab	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Job Crafting ->Job Performance	0.839	0.841	0.074	11.293	0.000
Job Crafting ->job engagement	0.836	0.829	0.078	10.728	0.000
Job Engagement -> Job Performance	0.968	0.968	0.004	20.024	0.000
Job Crafting -> Job Engagement -> Job Performance	0.809	0.803	0.076	10.623	0.000

To be more accurate, do the Sobel test: the results of the Sobel test with a calculator show result = 8.35421274 > 1.649949. Thus, based on the results of the H4 sobel test, it was declared accepted.

Based on table 8, it shows that the 4 hypotheses (H1, H2, H3, and H4) are accepted because they have P values <0.05.

DISCUSSION

Job Crafting and Job Performance

Job crafting means that employees design and re-interpret their jobs in ways that are personally meaningful (Berg, Dutton, & Wrzeniewski, 2013). The business/business sector of the economy/creative industry requires employees/leaders to continue to be creative and innovate in the production and post-production processes. Our empirical study shows that the performance of employees in the creative industries in Indonesia is good, this is one of the factors influenced by high job crafting. The results of this study are supported by Miraglia et al., 2017; Tims et al., 2015; Geldenhuys, M. et al. (2020); (Tims & Bakker, 2010. If employees are able to apply Job Crafting well, then employees will easily complete the job effectively and efficiently (Guan & Frenkel, 2018). Employees who arrange job characteristics well, are also able to arrange physical and mental aspects, relational well, correlated with tasks (Rosso et al., 2010); Bakker, A. B., Tims, M., & Derks, D. (2012); Berg, J. M., Dutton, J. E., & Wrzesniewski, A. (2013); Bindl, U. K., Unsworth, K. L., Gibson, C. B., & Stride, C. B. (2019).

Job Engagement and Job Performance

Job crafting makes work more valuable and meaningful for employees (Steger et al., 2012). Our next empirical findings show that job engagement has a strong positive attachment to the performance of creative industry employees in Indonesia. This means that the higher the level of employee involvement in work, the employee's performance will also increase. Allan et al., (2018); Kooij, D. T. A. M.; Tims, M. et al. (2012); Christian, et al. (2011); Tims, M., & Kanfer, R. (2015), proved that job engagement has an impact on employee performance.

Job Crafting Job Engagement

It is empirically proven that the two variables are strongly and significantly related to the creative industries in Indonesia. This means that the higher the level of job creation, the higher the job engagement. By being given freedom in designing and carrying out work according to individual characteristics with job characteristics it has an impact on employee work involvement that is more real. In this study, we adopted the JD-R approach (Bakker & Demerouti, 2013) because we were interested in how employee-driven changes in job characteristics contribute to job engagement and performance. With reference to the JD-R Theory, job crafting as an icon of individual factors which is an intangible resource owned by a company is a valuable, rare and crucial asset for improving performance is a key factor for obtaining sustainable competitive advantage and understanding competition (Tims et al., 2013). This theory is supported by empirical findings Albrecht, et al. (2015); Setyawati, S. M.

(2019); *Geldenhuys, et al. (2020)*; Van Wingerden, J. et al. (2015); Truxillo, D. M., et al. (2012); Petrou, P., et al. (2012); Hüseyin A. et al. (2019).

Job Crafting and Job Engagement and Job Performance

The last empirical findings prove that job engagement acts as a partial mediating variable in the relationship between job crafting and job performance in the creative industry/economy in Indonesia. Maximum employee performance can be achieved if job crafting and job engagement are maximized. High job crafting is characterized by: (1) high task crafting: employees do not hesitate to take on additional tasks, if the main task has been completed, giving preference to colleagues/others, introducing new work assignments that are more in line with skills or interests (2) Cognitive Crafting: often thinking about how to make work synergized with life goals, reminding oneself to contribute maximally to organizational goals and provide benefits to others. (3) Relational Crafting: trying hard to build a network/friendship, get along well with other people and help others (Leana, et al., (2009). Meanwhile, high job engagement is characterized by: Employees in the creative economy sector feel that they have energy, passion and strength at work; have high dedication to work; often immersed in work (Schaufeli, Bakker, & Salanova, 2006)

Creative industry employees in Indonesia are rated as high-performing leaders, meaning that leaders assess that employees at work have paid attention to quantity/work targets, quality, set time, cost/efficiency at work, good relations with colleagues and other parties, maintaining the company's name.

The results of this study are supported by a number of studies: Albana, H. (2019); Assen, The Netherlands: Koninklijke van Gorcum BV. Van Wingerden, J., Derks, D., & Bakker, A. B. (2015); Guan, X., & Frenkel, S. (2018); Rich, B. L., Lepine, J. A., & Crawford, E. R. (2010); Setyawati, S. M. (2019); Rich, B. L., Lepine, J. A., & Crawford, E. R. (2010); Tims, M., Bakker, A. B., Derks, D., & van Rhenen, W. (2013), Albana, H. (2019); Albrecht, S. L. (2013), which proves job engagement mediates the link between Job Crafting and Job performance.

CONCLUSION

The performance of creative industry/economy employees in Indonesia is categorized as good/high, job crafting and job engagement are also categorized as good/high and there is a relationship between job creation and performance and job engagement acts as a partial mediating variable. This means that to improve employee job performance it is also necessary to increase job crafting and job engagement. The research findings show that high employee performance is supported by a number of employee characteristics in the creative economy sector: they do not hesitate to give preference to others for work assignments that match their skills and interests, are more actively involved in building networks, the benefits of work are an important factor considered at work, and employees work enthusiastically, energetically, enthusiastically, and tenaciously at work.

Theoretical implications

The results of this study contribute to the HRM discipline to carry out the Job Demand Resources theory/approach which has proven to be relevant and tested in the creative economy in Indonesia.

Practical Implications

The results of this study uniquely contribute to policy makers related to the creative industry/economy in Indonesia that to produce optimal employee performance in the creative industry/economy it is necessary to increase job crafting and job engagement.

Research Limitations

As for the limitations of the study: (1) the assessment of all research variables was measured and analyzed at the level of employee perception and experience, so that the interpretation of research results may not reflect the actual conditions. (2) Data collection techniques using closed questionnaires allow objective reality to be bound by the questionnaire.

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